

STUDENTS SURVEY

72 responses

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1. What is your GPA?

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72 responses

2. In case you joined a studio course during the pandemic (COVID 19) crisis, which is a better studio setting?

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71 responses

3. Regarding your **INDIVIDUAL** project experience in the interior design (1) studio course, what did you achieve from the following *learning by doing* criteria? (you can tick more than 1 box)

72 responses

4. Regarding your **COLLABORATIVE** project experience in the interior design (1) studio course, what did you achieve from the following *learning by doing* criteria? (you can tick more than 1 box)

70 responses

5. What did the **COLLABORATIVE** project experience mainly achieve from the following points? (pick two only)

72 responses

6. **Potential learning** prepares students for their professional careers, which project encouraged potential learning more?

72 responses

7. If **potential learning** was achieved based on your opinion, how was it achieved? (pick two only)

71 responses

8. There're several of **technological interventions** in the design studio courses, which were the most beneficial in your interior (1) course? (pick two only)

70 responses

9. Based on the previous question, which project achieved the chosen *technological interventions*?

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70 responses

10. An effective teaching and learning process focuses on the design process instead of the final outcome, was this *process-focused* approach achieved?

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70 responses

11. Based on your previous answer, which criteria emphasize your *process-focused* answer? (pick two only)

70 responses

12. *Reflective learning* include 4 modes/phases respectively (habitual, understanding, reflection and critical reflection) to improve the student's learning skills, which phase did you reach in design course?

70 responses

13. Based on your previous answer, which project achieved *reflective learning*?

69 responses

14. Regarding your learning experience, how much are you satisfied with your **INDIVIDUAL PROJECT**?

72 responses

15. Regarding your learning experience, how much are you satisfied with your **COLLABORATIVE PROJECT**?

72 responses

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